

OPPOSITION-BASED FIREFLY ALGORITHM OPTIMIZED FEATURE SUBSET SELECTION APPROACH FOR FETAL RISK ANTICIPATION

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ABSTRACT

Recently huge amount of data is available in the field of medicine that helps the doctors in diagnosing diseases when analysed. Data mining techniques can be applied to these medical data to extract knowledge so that disease prediction becomes accurate and easier. In this work, cardiogram (CTG) data is analysed using Support Vector Machine (SVM) for predicting fetal risk. Opposition based firefly algorithm (OBFA) is proposed to extract the relevant features that maximise the classification performance of SVM. The obtained results show that opposition based firefly algorithm outperforms the standard firefly algorithm (FA).

KEYWORDS

Cardiogram, SVM Classifier, Feature Selection, Opposition-based firefly algorithm

1. INTRODUCTION

Cardiogram (CTG) is a commonly used technique to monitor and assess fetal state during pregnancy and delivery. It is a combination of two signals: fetal heart rate (FHR) and uterine contractions (UC). This CTG signal is used by obstetricians to monitor babies having either acute or chronic hypoxia. Visual analysis of CTG often leads to incorrect interpretations and hence computer aided systems are needed for classifying CTG which helps the obstetricians to decide if the baby can be given a natural birth or caesarean section.

Numerous methods have been reported in literature for analyzing the CTG data. A SVM classifier to classify the fetal state in to two classes [1]. Additionally, Genetic Algorithm has been used for selecting the most relevant features and thereby the performance of the classifier has been improved. Least squares-SVM, Particle Swarm Optimization and binary decision tree have been used to classify the CTG data [2]. An adaptive neuro fuzzy inference system has been presented to classify the CTG data of fetal state into two classes [3]. Classification of CTG data using Random forest classifier combined with feature reduction technique has been presented in [4]. Improved accuracy has been achieved using discriminant analysis, decision tree and artificial

neural network for fetal distress prediction in [5]. A classifier for CTG data which uses neural network and simple logistics is proposed in [6]. Naïve Bayes Classifier has been used for classification of CTG data along with feature selection approaches in [7]. A classifier which classifies the data into three classes by applying modular neural network is proposed in [8]. A neural network based classifier is proposed in [9] to improve the performance of other clustering algorithms in CTG classification. Naïve Bayes Classifier has been used in [10] to classify the CTG data in to three classes. In [11], a feature selection method based on Artificial Bee Colony algorithm is reported. Further, in [12] feature selection method based on Artificial Bee Colony algorithm and Support Vector Machines for medical datasets classification is proposed. A fetal state classifier using SVM and Firefly algorithm has been proposed in [13] to improve the classification accuracy of CTG. In [14], a genetic algorithm based feature subset selection is proposed to find the relevant features for CTG classification.

In this paper, opposition based firefly algorithm (OBFA) together with Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier has been proposed for classification of CTG data. OBFA has been used to produce optimal and reduced feature set which results in improvement of performance of the SVM classifier. Initially, CTG data are classified using the full feature set. Then, optimal feature set has been produced using FA and OBFA along with SVM classification. The experimental results reveal that the use of optimal feature set generated with OBFA improves the accuracy of classification.

This paper has been organized as follows; Section 2 describes the CTG data set. The Support Vector Machine classifier has been explained in section 3. Section 4 describes firefly algorithm and opposition based firefly algorithm (OBFA) is described in section 5. The proposed method of finding the optimal and reduced data set has been explained in the section 6 followed by the results and discussion in the section 7. Finally, the section 8 concludes the proposed method.

2. CTG DATA SET

The CTG dataset of UCI Machine Learning Repository [15] has been used for experiment. In this dataset, there are totally 2126 fetal cardiocograms belonging to three different classes with 21 attributes and 1 class attribute. Three expert obstetricians have classified this data set consisting measurements of fetal heart rate and uterine contractions and assigned classification labels to them based on the fetal heart rate class codes (N-Normal, S-Suspect and P-Pathologic).

2.1. Attribute Information

LB - FHR baseline (beats per minute)	Max - Maximum of FHR histogram
AC – No. of accelerations/second	Nmax - Number of histogram peaks
FM – No. of fetal movements/second	Nzeros - Number of histogram zeros
UC – No. of uterine contractions/second	Mode - Histogram mode
DL – No. of light decelerations/second	Mean - Histogram mean
DS – No. of severe decelerations/second	Median - Histogram median
DP – No. of prolonged decelerations/second	Variance - Histogram variance
Width - Width of FHR histogram	Tendency - Histogram tendency
Min - Minimum of FHR histogram	MSTV - Mean value of short term variability
ASTV - Percentage of time with abnormal short term variability	MLTV - Mean value of long term variability

ALTV - Percentage of time with abnormal long term variability CLASS- Fetal state class code
 (Normal=1; Suspect=2; Pathologic=3)

3. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE

Support vector machine (SVM) has been widely used for solving classification problems [16]. SVM separates the classes with an optimal hyperplane that increases the margin between the classes. The data points closest to this hyperplane are called support vectors. The nonlinear data used in this work is subjected to nonlinear kernel functions to transform the data into a new feature space where a hyperplane separates the data. Radial Basis Function (RBF) has been used widely by researchers for its better generalisation capability and hence RBF kernel has been adopted in this work. A One-Against-All SVM classifier is used here to classify the data into three classes.

4. FIREFLY ALGORITHM

Firefly algorithm is one of the efficient optimization algorithms [17]. Fireflies are insects producing a flashing light. Firefly algorithm makes use of three idealised rules. First, all fireflies are considered unisex which means that one firefly will be attracted to other fireflies regardless of their sex. Secondly, the degree of the attractiveness of a firefly is proportion to its light intensity, thus for any two flashing fireflies, the less brighter one will move towards the more brighter one. Finally, the light intensity of a firefly is somehow related with the analytical form of the fitness function. The basic steps of the FA are summarized as the pseudo code shown in figure 1.

```

begin
  Fitness function  $f(M)$ ,  $M=(m_1, \dots, m_d)^c$ 
  Generate initial population of fireflies  $M_i(i=1, \dots, n)$ 
  Brightness  $L_i$  at  $M_i$  is determined by  $f(M_i)$ 
  Define light absorption coefficient  $\alpha$ 
   $s=1$ 
  while ( $s < s_{\max}$ )
    for  $i=1:n$  all  $n$  fireflies
      for  $j=1:n$  all  $n$  fireflies
        if ( $L_j > L_i$ )
          Move firefly  $i$  towards  $j$  in  $d$ -dimension
        end if
        Attractiveness varies with distance via  $\exp[-\alpha p^2]$ 
        Evaluate new solutions and update brightness
      end for  $j$ 
    end for  $i$ 
    Rank the fireflies and find the current best
     $s=s+1$ 
  end while
  Post process results and visualization
end

```

Figure 1. Pseudocode of the standard firefly algorithm

The dimension of the function to be optimized is given by d , n is the number of fireflies, s_{\max} is the maximum number of generations, α is the light absorption coefficient, L_i is the light intensity

and the distance p between any two fireflies i and j located at positions M_i and M_j can be evaluated as follows.

$$p_{ij} = \text{Distance}(M_i, M_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^d (m_{i,k} - m_{j,k})^2} \quad (1)$$

The light intensity (L) decreases as the square of the distance increases (p^2). It can be approximated using the following form.

$$L(p) = L_0 e^{-\alpha p^2} \quad (2)$$

where, L_0 is the light intensity at source. As the firefly's attractiveness is proportional to the light intensity, we can define the attractiveness σ as follows;

$$\sigma(p) = \sigma_0 e^{-\alpha p^2} \quad (3)$$

Here, σ_0 is the attractiveness at $p = 0$. Now the movement of a firefly i attracted to another more attractive firefly j is given by,

$$m_{i+1} = m_i + \sigma_0 e^{-\alpha p_{ij}^2} (m_j - m_i) + \lambda(\text{rand}() - 0.5) \quad (4)$$

where, λ is the randomization parameter and $\text{rand}()$ is a random number generator.

Even though the standard FA outperforms the other evolutionary algorithms like genetic algorithm it faces some difficulties like premature convergence and obtaining better solutions.

5. OPPOSITION-BASED FIREFLY ALGORITHM

In order to overcome the above mentioned problems of FA, a novel approach called opposition-based learning (OBL) suggested by Tizhoosh [18] has been applied with FA. It has been successfully applied with several optimisation algorithms like genetic algorithm, differential evolution algorithm, ant colony optimisation and gravitational search algorithm. In OBL the candidate solution and its corresponding opposite solution are considered simultaneously. Let $z \in [x, y]$ be a real number, the opposite number of z is denoted as z^{\wedge} and is defined as:

$$z^{\wedge} = x + y - z \quad (5)$$

The above concept can be extended to the case of higher dimensions. Let $Q(z_1, z_2, \dots, z_m)$ be a m -dimensional vector, where $z_i \in [x_i, y_i]$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. The opposite vector of Q is defined by $Q^{\wedge} = (z_1^{\wedge}, z_2^{\wedge}, \dots, z_m^{\wedge})$, where $z_i^{\wedge} = x_i + y_i - z_i$.

The proposed algorithm applies OBL concept in two phases of optimisation namely initialising the population and producing new generations.

Initially a population of n fireflies is generated. The opposite position of each firefly is computed using equation 5. Each firefly is evaluated using the fitness function and the n fittest individuals are selected from the total of $2n$ individuals based on the fitness value. The basic steps of the OBFA are shown as pseudo code in figure 2.

Additionally, the OBFA uses OBL technique for producing new generations and updating the firefly's positions. In this method, e fireflies yielding the worst fitness values are replaced by their opposite fireflies at each iteration of the optimization process. At the start, variable e should possess a larger value to provide an effective global search. As the iteration increases, the value of e should be reduced to provide a local exploitation. Therefore, the value of e is given as follows:

$$e = \text{Round} \left[\frac{n}{3} \left(1 - \frac{s}{s_{\max}} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

where, Round (x) rounds the value of x to the nearest integer and s_{\max} is the maximum number of generations.

```

begin
  Fitness function  $f(M)$ ,  $M=(m_1, \dots, m_d)^c$ 
  Generate initial population of fireflies  $M_i(i=1, \dots, n)$ 
  Generate opposite population of fireflies  $OM_i(i=1, \dots, n)$ 
  Find the fittest population  $n$  from  $\{M_i, OM_i\}$  as initial population
  Brightness  $L_i$  at  $M_i$  is determined by  $f(M_i)$ 
  Define light absorption coefficient  $\alpha$ 
   $s=1$ 
  while ( $s < s_{\max}$ )
    for  $i=1:n$  all  $n$  fireflies
      for  $j=1:n$  all  $n$  fireflies
        if ( $L_j > L_i$ )
          Move firefly  $i$  towards  $j$  in  $d$ -dimension
        end if
        Attractiveness varies with distance via  $\exp[-\alpha p^2]$ 
        Evaluate new solutions and update brightness
        Calculate  $e$  based on equation 6
        Change  $e$  worst fireflies with their opposite using equation 5
      end for  $j$ 
    end for  $i$ 
    Rank the fireflies and find the current best
     $s=s+1$ 
  end while
  Post process results and visualization
end

```

Figure 2. Pseudocode of proposed OBFA algorithm

6. PROPOSED OBFA OPTIMIZED FEATURE SUBSET SELECTION USING SVM

Feature selection is the process of excluding irrelevant features which may otherwise degrade the performance of the classifier. Feature selection is performed either as wrapper based or filter based. Wrapper based methods make use of the performance of a classifier to evaluate the feature subsets. On the other hand, the filter based methods use feature evaluation techniques.

In this work, SVM classifier is used to classify the CTG data with the complete set of 21 features. In addition, FA and OBFA has been used with SVM for finding the optimal feature subset. The features of the dataset are represented as a binary string of 0's and 1's. The value of 1 (one) represents the presence of a particular feature and 0 (zero) represents its absence. The whole data set is divided in to 75% (1594 instances) and 25% (532 instances) and used for training and testing the classifier respectively. 10 fold cross validation is applied to the training set and the testing set is completely hidden from the classifier during training.

The fitness function (F) is given by,

$$F = E_c + w_1 T_f \quad (7)$$

where, E_c is average accuracy rate of SVM classifier and T_f is number of zeros (absence of feature) in the feature subset and w_1 is the weight which is equal to 0.1. The parameters of Firefly algorithm are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Firefly algorithm parameters

Number of fireflies	30
Number of generations	100
Randomisation parameter (λ)	0.5
Attractiveness (σ)	0.2
Light absorption coefficient (α)	1

7. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Experiments have been performed using the original dataset and the optimal reduced data subset. The various performance measures being considered and their expressions are listed from equations (8) to (15).

$$\text{Accuracy} = \left[\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \left[\frac{TP}{TP + FN} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \left[\frac{TN}{TN + FP} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Positive Predictive Value (Precision): } PPV = \left[\frac{TP}{TP + FP} \right] \quad (11)$$

$$\text{Negative Predictive Value: } NPV = \left[\frac{TN}{TN + FN} \right] \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Geometric mean: } G_{\text{mean}} = \sqrt{\text{specificity} \times \text{sensitivity}} \tag{13}$$

$$\text{F-measure} = 2 \times \left[\frac{\text{precision} \times \text{sensitivity}}{\text{precision} + \text{sensitivity}} \right] \tag{14}$$

$$\text{Area under ROC} = \frac{\text{specificity} + \text{sensitivity}}{2} \tag{15}$$

where, TP - True Positives, TN - True Negatives, FP - False Positives and FN - False Negatives
The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of SVM accuracy with and without feature selection

	Data set	Average accuracy (%)
Without FS	Full feature set	88.75
With FS	FA	91.92
	OBFA	92.85

It is found that the average accuracy is 88.75% with full feature set and the same is achieved as 91.92% with optimal feature set produced by FA and as 92.85% with optimal feature set produced by OBFA.

Table 3. Performance metrics of SVM with and without feature selection

Performance Metrics (%)	Without FS	With FS	
		FA	OBFA
Sensitivity	77.30	84.83	83.81
Specificity	90.22	93.78	93.72
PPV	78.56	83.14	85.45
NPV	90.70	93.26	95.02
G-mean	82.92	89.19	88.62
F-measure	77.92	83.94	84.62
Area under ROC	83.76	89.30	88.76

The results given in tables 2 and 3 are depicted in graphical form in figures 3 and 4 respectively for a better illustration.

Figure 3. Comparison of SVM accuracy with and without feature selection

Figure 4. Performance metrics of SVM with and without feature selection

Tables 2 and 3 and figures 4 and 5 show the performance measures of SVM using the full feature set, optimal feature set using FA and OBFA. The results show that OBFA performs better than FA and full feature set.

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, Opposition based Firefly algorithm is proposed for producing optimal feature set for CTG classification. CTG dataset from UCI Machine Learning Repository has been taken for experimentation. The classification results are presented in terms of Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity, Positive Predictive Value, Negative Predictive Value, Geometric Mean, F-measure and Area under ROC. The results of experiments show that there is a marginal improvement in the performance of proposed OBFA optimized classifier than the existing FA optimized classifier. However, there is a significant improvement in the performance of the proposed classifier when compared to the classifier with full feature set (without feature selection). This improvement in performance will ensure that the obstetricians can make more accurate decisions from CTG recordings.

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